

CROP RESIDUES AS FIBROUS AND FUNCTIONAL COMPOUNDS FOR PAPER PRODUCTION

Ilja Gasan Osojnik Črnivec¹, Mija Sežun², Mihaela Skrt¹, Tea Kapun²,
Nataša Poklar Ulrih^{1,3}

¹ University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Food Science
and Technology, Ljubljana, Slovenia

²Pulp and Paper Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³The Centre of Excellence for Integrated Approaches in Chemistry and Biology
of Proteins (CipKeBiP), Ljubljana, Slovenia

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natasa.poklar@bf.uni-lj.si

Abstract: *Due to the high lignocellulose content, as well as the high content of phenolic compounds, agro-industrial vegetable waste is well suited for valorization in packaging materials. As specialized packing materials, these materials may offer competitive advantages to paper producers, utilizing a low cost feedstock to produce a bespoke product of good quality. In our contribution, we focus on the production residues of various plant streams (e.g. growing and processing of onions, olives and pomegranates), to demonstrate how such diverse agro-industrial bio-waste materials could be fully exploited even before their reformulation. Onion skins and olive leaves both showed high antioxidant activity and the possibility to recover relatively high yields of bioactive compounds (roughly 100 mg of quercetin or oleuropein per g of dry extract). However, in pomegranate peel, the content of the antocyanins (roughly 0.3 mg of antocyanins per g of dry extract) was low. All three plant residues sources produced unique paper materials. Olive skins and olive leaves were used as two individual feedstocks, whereas the pomegranate peel was required to be added to cellulose. The resulting papers exhibited good technological properties, as well as interesting texture and appearance and might as such be suited for the production of special papers. The determined characteristics of the samples demonstrate a good potential for cascading use*

where paper production should be further studied following the extraction of bioactive components.

Keywords: crop residues, vegetable residues, bioactive compounds, paper production

1 INTRODUCTION

Accumulation of agro-industrial residues is an enormous untapped resource, and is tied to several negative aspects when left unexploited, such as unnecessary production of biomass, high costs of waste management, environmental issues such as eutrophication and greenhouse gas emission and several interlocking social aspects. In 2018, the European Union generated 85.4 million tons of bio-waste from agriculture and food production (excluding animal feces, urine and manure), which amounted to 3% of all waste produced. The predominant treatment of this waste included recycling (93%, including composting and anaerobic digestion) and energy recovery (5%) (EUROSTAT, 2021). These waste-management treatments are more efficient and environmentally sound than landfill and incineration. However, such diverse agro-industrial bio-waste material should be fully exploited before its biodegradation and/or conversion to energy, as these final operations can destroy many valuable components.

Agro-industrial waste of plant origin is typically particularly rich in bioactive compounds and lignocellulose content. The bioactive contents of agro-industrial residues, and especially the phenolic compounds in fruit and vegetable waste, are gaining attention in the food industry. As it has been extensively demonstrated by our research group (e.g. Terpinc et al., 2012; Abram et al., 2015; Cifà et al., 2018; Osojnik Črnivec et al., 2021), these parts can be used as a natural, cheap and easily accessible source of antioxidants for food fortification.

Furthermore, the long term growth of the packaging industry is driven by the development of high-performance renewable materials. Recent consumer market trends in Europe have shifted toward sustainable packaging solutions (i.e. packaging made from recyclables, re-usable packaging, reducing material use through lightweighting, and bio-based polymers) (Parker, 2008). Environmental policies encourage the creation of natural fiber-based products as well as the reuse of as much material as possible (Kozłowski & Mackiewicz Talarczyk, 2020). Developing packaging materials from renewable and bio-based sources has become critical, not only to address and prudently valorize

waste disposal issues, but also to reduce stubble burning and save timber resources. Valorization and conversion of renewable agro-waste to biodegradable composites has proven to be a significant breakthrough in the packaging area (Bhardwaj et al., 2020).

In the present study we aim to demonstrate further possibilities for the utilization of fibrous components in widely abundant plant residues rich in bioactives and lignocellulose (onion skins, pomegranate peels, olive leaves) and examine aspects that would enable their cascading use (i.e. exploitation of extracts for food or other use in the first stage, followed by reformulation into novel materials).

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Residues from plant production

Onion skin (i.e. the onion (*Allium cepa* L. var. *cepa*) outer tunic layer of the yellow onion variety without any of the dry scape, leaves, the reduced stem and roots) was obtained as air-dried commercial waste from onion farming from the Celje region in Slovenia. Pomegranate fruits (*Punica granatum* L.) of various varieties were obtained from local farms in the Slovenian Istria. The fruits were manually peeled and the peel was further freeze dried and stored at -20 °C until further use. Olive leaves (i.e. the olive (*Olea europaea* L.) leaves and stem clippings of the variety “*Istrska belica*”) were collected from the orchard Školarice from Slovenian Istria. The olive leaves were air-dried at 25 °C for 7 days.

2.2 Chemical and physical analysis of the samples

Cellulose, holocellulose and hemicellulose contents were determined extraction of the samples in hexane and ethanol and by quantification of the remaining material. Acid - insoluble lignin (Klason's lignin) content was determined by hydrolyzing and dissolving the carbohydrates from the sample with sulfur acid and by filtration, drying and quantification of the remaining insolubilized lignin. Three- step extraction in 70% ethanol was performed as an analytical extraction for HPLC analysis, as well as a commercially feasible approach for the recovery of bioactives (Cifà et al., 2018; Osojnik Črnivec et al., 2021).

2. 3 Determination of bioactive substances

Antioxidant capacity of the plant residues was determined with the DPPH* antioxidant assay (Brand-Williams et al., 1995). The antioxidant capacity was expressed in mass equivalents of Trolox (TE).

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; Infinity 1260; Agilent Technologies) was used to analyze the content of model bioactive compounds or compound groups in each of the plant sources. The analyzed bioactives (onion skin – quercetin, pomegranate peel - anthocyanins, olive leaves – oleuropein) were selected on the basis of their predominant activity and/or content. The analytical extracts were passed through a C18 precolumn (Eclipse XBD; 4.6 × 12.5 mm, I.D. 5 µm) and a C18 column (Zorbax Eclipse Plus; 4.6 × 150 mm, I.D. 3.5 µm) (both from Agilent Technologies). The components were separated with gradient elution with analyte-specific mobile phases and determined on a UV–Vis diode array detector (quercetin was monitored at 370 nm, anthocyanins at 520 nm, and oleuropein at 280 nm).

2. 4 Papermaking and determination of its optical and mechanical properties

The fibers were isolated from rough biomass in the delignification process (removal of the lignin that is binding the fibers together) carried out in a 5 L rotation autoclave digester (Universal Engineering Corporation, India) at working conditions (time, temperature, addition of NaOH and Na₂S, liquid/solid ratio) which were fine-tuned to each biomass.

The delignified biomass was further disintegrated in a laboratory disintegrator, when required, and then screened by the Sommerville (Universal Engineering Corporation, India) laboratory fractionator using a sieve with 45 mm x 0.15 mm slots. The obtained fibers were characterized for their morphological and technological papermaking properties (grammage (ISO 536), thickness (ISO 534), tensile properties (ISO 1924–2), tearing resistance (ISO 1974), bursting strength (ISO 2758), roughness according to Bendtsen (ISO 8791–2), ISO whiteness (ISO 2470–1) and opacity (ISO 2471)). Morphological properties such as fiber length, width and cell wall thickness were also determined in fiber suspension with a fiber analyzer (Valmet Automation Inc., Finland).

Finally, paper sheets were prepared on a Rapid-Köthen sheet forming machine (PTI, Austria).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial plant production residues were characterized for their fibrous and bioactive content, and the amount of material that might be removed during the extraction step of bioactive was determined, as well (Table 1). The plant material that was selected for selected for our study was based on the availability of the material, as well as the initial content of bioactive compounds. For example, we have previously demonstrated that in the waste fraction of yellow onion the quercetin content and antioxidant capacity were 50-60% lower in comparison to red onion and red shallots (Osojnik Črnivec et al., 2021). However, as the yellow onion and still contains considerably high amounts of bioactives (allowing the retrieval of 200 mg of quercetin per kg of dry produce) and is the main type of onion on the market and in processing, we identify its skin residue as the most promising fraction for re-use. Similarly, content of bioactive compounds is shown in Table 1 which was high for onion skin, onion leaves and low for pomegranate peel, ultimately enabling the recovery of 100 mg quercetin, 80 mg of oleuropein and 0.3 mg anthocyanins, respectively, per g DM of the corresponding extract.

Antioxidant capacity was determined by the DPPH* assay which provides more robust values, as compared to other antioxidant assays, and might therefore be more suited for bulk biomass comparisons and designing potential applications (Miklavčič Višnjevca et al., 2017; Osojnik Črnivec et al., 2021;). The antioxidant capacity reflected the amount of the analyzed compounds and was high for onion skins and olive leaves and several orders of magnitude lower for pomegranate peels.

Table 1: Fibrous and bioactive components and antioxidant capacity of the samples.

Group	Parameter	Samples		
		Onion skins	Olive leaves	Pomegranate peels
Fibrous content	Cellulose (% DM)	36.4	14.4	11.0
	Hemicellulose (% DM)	33.1	37.1	11.6
	Lignin (% DM)	3.5	19.6	12.2
Extractives	In 70% ethanol (% DM)	9.06	46.5	68.2
Bioactive content	Quercetin (mg/g DM)	10.03 ±0.29	n.d.	n.d.
	Oleuropein (mg/g DM)	n.d.	37.2 ±0.1	n.d.
	Anthocyanins (mg/g DM)	n.d.	n.d.	0.1685 ±0.0001
Antioxidant capacity	DPPH* assay (mg TE/g DM)	19.78 ±0.17	212 ±2.0	0.0116 ±0.0041

DM – dry matter, data are means ±SD, n.d. – not determined, TE – Trolox equivalent

Within the parameters that are relevant for paper production, onion skin had the highest amount of cellulose and the lowest amount of the lignin compared to olive leaves and pomegranate peels. Amongst these materials, onion skin ranks among the potential alternative raw material for papermaking, and may even not require delignification.

Furthermore, taking in account the possible step bioactive compound recovery, relatively a small fraction (less than 10%) was removed by extraction of onion skins in 70% ethanol, while still providing a quercetin/ antioxidant rich extract. In the other cases, half (olive leaves) or even more than three thirds (pomegranate peel) of the dry matter could be removed by the extraction procedure. Nevertheless, for the purpose of paper making, all of these streams could actually benefit from the extraction in aqueous ethanol solvents, as they would increase the overall content of the remaining structural compounds.

Although it can be expected that by removing extractable components the technological properties of the paper might improve (e.g. in the best case increasing the cellulose content of the onion skins to >50%, pomegranate peels to >35% and olive leaves to >25%) it is important to study and/or modify the extraction procedure to prevent dissolution of cellulose during the same process.

The mechanical and optical characteristics of the isolated fibers (Table 2) are similar (length-weighted values), with pomegranate peels exhibiting the widest fibers and most pronounced fibrillation. The curl was most expressed by fibers from the onion skin. Overall, the fibers are short, when compared to deciduous and coniferous trees and the biggest resemblance to deciduous trees are exhibited by olive leaves.

Table 2: Mechanical and optical characteristics

Parameter	Samples		
	Onion skins	Olive leaves	Pomegranate peels
<i>Fibre width (μm)</i>	32.36	31.93	39.82
<i>Curl (%)</i>	11.34	8.58	9.91
<i>Fibrillation (%)</i>	2.09	3.52	4.45
<i>Lc(l) ISO (μm)</i>	261	583	112

Fibre width Curl and fibre length (Lc(Lc(l) ISO) are given as length-weighted values. Fibrillation is given as a percentage of the projection area of fibrils in relation to projection area of the entire object.

Paper sheets were prepared to simulate the industrial process of paper production (Table 3). Onion skin had the highest proportion of cellulose (>30%) amongst all samples, benefiting the preparation and the quality of the paper.

Despite a decrease of the morphological properties, which may require an optimization of delignification, the resulting paper exhibited good mechanical properties. Olive leaves and pomegranate peels had slightly worse results to onion skin, which are reflected in the content of cellulose. Pomegranate peels required addition of cellulose, where pomegranate impaired mechanical properties (tension, tensile strength and bursting strength), reduced whiteness, and increases opacity and roughness, and provided an interesting texture.

Table 3: Optical and mechanical properties of paper

Parameter	Samples			
	Onion skins (100%)	Olive leaves (100%)	Pomegranate peels/ cellulose (15/ 85%)	Cellulose (100%)
<i>Grammage (g/m²)</i>	67.9	37.4	63.6	65.0
<i>Thickness (um)</i>	115	144	161	116
<i>Tensile index (Nm/g)</i>	39.3	9.9	41.4	53.3
<i>Breaking length (km)</i>	4.010	1.009	4.222	5.334
<i>Bendtsen roughness (ml/min)</i>	518	1991	1677	342
<i>ISO whiteness (%)</i>	14.5	18.6	41.4	77.0
<i>Opacity (%)</i>	99.7	94.4	96.8	86.6
<i>Tear index (mNm²/g)</i>	2.09	2.80	7.35	7.85
<i>Burst index (KNm/g)</i>	1.75	1.02	2.65	3.48

Cellulose composition (80% eucalyptus, 20% conifers, ground to 30 SR)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In our contribution we demonstrate paper production from plant production residues and indicate further pathways for prior recovery of bioactives from these biomass streams, as reformulation into paper can destroy many valuable components. Our initial characterization also indicates, that for the development of cascading use of these residues, a feasible compromise between partial dissolution of cellulose (by ethanol-water mixtures) and recovery of bioactive compounds has yet to be identified.

The obtained papers show that compared to 100% cellulose alternative sources like our samples can be used through some optimization to obtain good quality paper. The use of plant residues or addition of plant residues to cellulose also produced interesting and attractive colors and textures, providing characteristics that can improve the appearance and feel, which are particularly valuable for special papers.

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